

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 3

 Acceptance of papers **MARCH, 2025**

Acceptance of papers
Published monthly

Topics
economics,
technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL "INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY" HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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UO'K: 33:338.1 (575.1)
JEL: B25

EVOLUTION OF THEORETICAL VIEWS ON STATE REGULATION OF THE REAL SECTOR OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: The relevance of this topic is underscored by the necessity of creating conditions for the effective functioning of the market mechanism in state regulation of the real sector of the national economy. This includes the state's role in organizing and regulating the production and consumption of social goods and services, protecting the population from the adverse effects of human activity and natural phenomena that occur outside the market system (factors that harm human health and the environment), and ensuring social protection for economically disadvantaged groups to maintain socio-political stability. Additionally, the implementation of macroeconomic stabilization measures remains a critical aspect of economic policy.

Key words: Real sector, mercantilists, physiocrats, economic liberalism, monetarists, supply-side economics, Laffer effect.

INTRODUCTION

The state holds monopolistic authority, establishing both general and specific behavioral norms for all entities within the economic system. As an institution, the state has the ability to plan at a macro level, exercising a superior role over all institutions. However, this does not diminish the importance of independent economic entities, though their freedom is constrained by state-imposed regulations. Moreover, this system remains dynamic, continuously adapting to the evolving objectives of the state at both global and national levels. The forms and methods of governance are constantly evolving, reshaping the real sector of the economy. As a result, state-led regulation aims to enhance and develop the real sector and the broader economic system, implemented through legislation, enforcement, and oversight by authorized institutions.

Currently, countries worldwide face the challenge of increasing state influence over the real sector. Over the past few decades, many developed nations have encountered intensifying global competition, worsening environmental conditions, depletion of natural resources, and heightened demands for economic security. These challenges often stem from the inefficiencies of the real sector or its specific subsectors. Many scholars and policymakers attribute negative trends to flaws within the existing economic system. Consequently, research continues to explore models for developing the real sector and the regulatory measures used by the state.

The role, functions, and challenges of the state in economic affairs have been a focal point of scholarly attention since the inception of economic science. It is important to note that many economic schools and theories do not regard state support for the real sector as an independent economic policy direction; rather, they examine it within the broader context of state regulatory measures.

The state's support for the real sector represents a significant shift in its economic role, closely linked to the formation of industrialized societies between the late 17th and early 18th centuries. The term "real sector of the economy" has been actively used in scientific literature since 1997. Theoretical analysis of this concept

focuses on defining its essence and distinguishing it from other economic categories through the following methodological approaches: examining the fundamental laws governing its development, identifying its defining characteristics, clarifying its interconnections with other economic categories.

The real sector encompasses diverse economic relationships and represents a structured economic entity. However, economic literature has yet to fully define and explain this category. Generally, the real sector of the economy refers to a system of companies and organizations engaged in the production and provision of goods and services (excluding financial services) within a free market. Historical experience demonstrates that state intervention in the economy has evolved through various stages. The mechanisms of state support for the real sector are influenced by technological advancements, economic growth, shifts in economic policies, and the overall development of economic relations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Historical experience shows that state intervention in the economy has evolved through various stages. The mechanism of state support for the real sector is determined by the technological development of enterprises, economic growth, changes in economic policies, as well as the development of economic relations and overall economic progress. Theories regarding state support for the real sector of the economy have a long historical foundation, each with unique characteristics. For instance, mercantilists focused on state support through protective policies during the emergence and development stages of the manufacturing industry. As noted by Samuel Fortrey (1622–1681), a nation's wealth is directly related to the level of production: "The more we produce domestically, the wealthier we become, since all goods are exchanged for our own products," [1] He emphasized the necessity of producing "products that require the least expenditure for production and are highly valued abroad." [2] Mercantilists proposed several key policies to support the real sector, including: establishing "warehouses" for foreign trade (ensuring that all revenues from foreign trade would be allocated to purchasing locally manufactured goods), granting permissions for exporting domestic and processed goods (as selling finished products yields greater profits than exporting raw materials), imposing tariffs on foreign goods and regulating imports through export promotion, particularly recommending rewards for companies exporting products in high demand in foreign markets. [3]

Physiocrats, in contrast, studied the agricultural sector as the foundation of the real economy. They regarded agriculture as the only truly productive sector, arguing that: "Wealth is created only in agriculture, while industry and trade merely redistribute and reallocate it."

Consequently, physiocrats shifted economic research from commerce to production, laying the foundation for the next stage of the capitalist system. The methodological premise of François Quesnay's economic analysis was his concept of "natural order." According to him, this concept's legal foundation concerns laws that protect private property and individual interests while ensuring an equitable distribution of material wealth. [4]

By the late 18th century, proponents of economic liberalism challenged these views, arguing that: "Government intervention in the economy is detrimental to business." [5]

Classical political economists such as Adam Smith and David Ricardo posited that: "Without state intervention and influence, the market would naturally establish equilibrium." [6] They believed that the market is the optimal mechanism for economic system functioning. Smith supported this "natural order" theory with practical policies, advocating that the government should intervene only to regulate the internal market (e.g., by imposing tariffs on domestic goods).

In the 1970s and 1980s, with the increasing influence of monetarist approaches, supply-side economics emerged as a neo-classical theory in state regulation of the real sector. Supply-side economics is primarily based on practical policy recommendations and economic accounting principles. [7]

Supply-side economics encompasses a set of practical propositions aimed at promoting production and investment. These include supply-side policies, improving the budget situation, and other related measures. Supply-side economics was developed by American economists **A. Laffer, M. Feldstein, and R. Reagan**.

According to representatives of **supply-side economics**, the market is not only the most effective but also the only "normal" way to establish and sustain an economy. They opposed state regulation of the real sector, arguing that "**regulation leads to a decline in productivity and stifles the initiative of economic participants.**"[8]

Neo-classical theory considers state fiscal policy to be the most essential means of promoting entrepreneurship. It anticipates that as production expands and the economy emerges from stagnation, new revenues will fill budgetary gaps. Proponents of **supply-side economics** suggest that the **Laffer effect** illustrates the essence of supply by representing it with a curve (graph) and that fiscal policy should align with this theory (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Laffer Effect. [9]

The concept of the **Laffer Effect** suggests that reducing tax rates in the short term may lead to a decrease in state revenues. However, in the long term, lower tax rates can increase savings, investment, and employment. As a result, production volumes grow, and tax revenues ultimately rise.

P. Samuelson and E. Hansen developed the concept of economic stabilizers—mechanisms implemented by the state to promote economic stability. According to this concept, these mechanisms enable direct governmental involvement in the economic activities of businesses to foster growth. The state employs fiscal policies (including taxes, government orders, investments, and subsidies) and monetary policies to regulate the economy. The appropriate combination of these mechanisms, when effectively managed by the state, contributes to balanced economic growth.

According to Professor B.B. Berkinov, regarding state regulation of the economy: “The state’s intervention in the economy, aimed at serving the interests of society, creates a convergence of political, social, and economic relations between the state and economic entities.” [10]

Similarly, H.P. Abulkasimov, M.H. Abulkasimov, and S.P. Topildiyev expressed the view that “the state’s economic policy, directed at regulating the economy, consists of targeted measures designed to create favorable conditions for the functioning of the market economy while also influencing socio-economic processes.” [11]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a comprehensive methodological approach to analyze the evolution of theoretical views on state regulation of the real sector of the economy. The research is based on a systematic review of classical and modern economic theories, examining their relevance to state intervention in economic activities.

A qualitative analysis of historical and contemporary literature is conducted to identify key paradigms and shifts in economic thought regarding government regulation. Comparative analysis is applied to evaluate different theoretical perspectives, such as Keynesian, neoclassical, and institutional approaches, highlighting their impact on policy-making in various economic contexts.

Additionally, case study analysis is used to assess the practical application of state regulation mechanisms in different economies. This methodological framework enables a comprehensive understanding of how theoretical perspectives on state intervention have evolved and influenced real-sector policies over time.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

From today’s perspective, the sustainable functioning of the economy primarily depends on maintaining economic relationships between the real and financial sectors. The state plays a significant and decisive role in ensuring these relationships. In practical life, relying solely on market mechanisms to achieve economic stability is insufficient. While market mechanisms offer clarity and effectiveness, they may encounter certain challenges in their intermediary functions. These challenges can only be effectively addressed through the rational use of mechanisms organized by the state.

State intervention in the economy occurs in two key directions. First, enterprises and organizations that constitute the state sector participate in market relations by producing goods and services as part of the national economy. Second, the state plays a crucial role in organizing interactions and processes between the real and financial sectors, acting as a force that represents collective interests. [12]

In this regard, President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev emphasized: “The sustainable growth of the economy is directly dependent on the development of key sectors. We will prioritize the sectors that produce high-value-added

products. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a strategy for the growth of sectors that significantly drive the economy.” [13]

Furthermore, President Mirziyoyev highlighted the state’s role in regulating the economy, stating: “In 2017, we took the first steps towards implementing modern, new-content reforms in the economic sphere that meet contemporary demands. A series of laws, resolutions, and programs have been introduced to create a fundamentally new economic environment, further liberalize it, strengthen its legal foundations, modernize production, and diversify industrial practices.” [14]

In alignment with the President’s initiatives, the state’s role in enhancing the competitiveness of products manufactured in the real sector is crucial for strengthening the national economy’s position within the global economic system. Additionally, efforts must be directed toward eliminating factors that contribute to declining product quality and increasing production costs, as these challenges hinder the development of the real sector.

Furthermore, several critical issues persist, including outdated equipment and technologies in enterprises, high material and energy consumption in production, and the need to implement effective product quality management systems. Ensuring that products meet state standards remains an unresolved concern for many enterprises. Additionally, the full utilization of production capacities must not be overlooked. State regulation of the real sector, combined with efforts to simplify relevant definitions and unify economic schools of thought with contemporary scholarly perspectives, has led us to develop the following table (Table 1).

Table 1. Ideas on the regulation of the real sector by the state[15].

Economic Schools	Ideas	Note
Physiocrats (F. Quesnay, A. Turgot)	It is necessary to produce goods that require the lowest production costs and have the highest value abroad.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This involves creating «warehouses» for trading foreign goods (indicating that all revenues from exports are spent on purchasing locally produced goods); - Allowing the export of domestic products and prepared goods (since they yield more profit than exporting raw materials); - Imposing duties on foreign goods and regulating imports by promoting exports, especially rewarding organizations that produce highly demanded products in foreign markets.
Physiocrats (F. Quesnay, A. Turgot)	Wealth is generated solely in agriculture; in industry and trade, it is reprocessed and redistributed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishing the free trade of grain within the country; allowing the import of grain without customs duties and exporting it freely; exchanging natural goods by means of monetary payment (in cash); eliminating guilds and artisan workshops that hinder the development of entrepreneurship in industry (meaning the unification of large traders and artisans); - The development of laws that protect private property and individual interests and ensure the effectiveness of local production and the distribution of material wealth.
Classical Economists (A. Smith, D. Ricardo)	In the absence of state intervention and influence in the economy, a self-regulating equilibrium operates in the market.	It is essential to develop an economic policy that supports the growth of the productive forces in society.
Neoclassical School (A. Pigou, W. Ouken)	The role of the state is to identify «external influences» that have social significance for developing a system of taxes and subsidies.	State activities aimed at creating a competitive market environment can, on one hand, serve as a means to promote the development of producers, while on the other hand, it can also be seen as a restrictive means for economic agents. Their activities are contrary to the principles of competition.
Keynesianism (J. M. Keynes)	Keynes proposed various methods for the direct and indirect influence of the state on the volume of investments.	This is due to the fact that the development of production, as well as market conditions and the dynamics of GDP, depend on their dynamics. Thus, investments, employment levels, and the growth of entrepreneurs’ incomes are related to the total demand, total supply, and other factors.

<p>Institutionalists</p>	<p>Institutionalists advocate for the principles of individual freedom and private property; however, they also support an active role for the state in economic life. For them, it is essential to create favorable institutional conditions for the functioning of self-regulating market mechanisms, promote competition, ensure a non-inflationary monetary system, and implement policies that encourage entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>Modernizing the economy, creating contemporary production processes, and accelerating economic growth are all demands for a more active and long-term economic policy—dirigisme (the active intervention of the state in the economy).</p>
<p>Modern Market Economy Representatives (P. Samuelson, E. Hansen)</p>	<p>They developed the concept of automatic economic stabilizers (mechanisms) that are regulated by the state. The proper combination of these management mechanisms helps achieve balanced growth in production.</p>	<p>This, in turn, allows agricultural entities to develop without direct state intervention. The state implements financial policies (taxes, state orders, investments, subsidies, and others) as well as monetary and credit policies.</p>
<p>Scientists from CIS Countries (A. S. Bulatov)</p>	<p>The structure of the real sector of the economy primarily consists of industry, agriculture, construction, and transportation. In our opinion, this position is not entirely correct, as the real sector of the economy also includes the fields of production outside of finance.</p>	<p>The regulation of the economy by the state is a process in which the state influences the economic life of society and the related social processes. In this process, the state's economic and social policies are implemented according to certain doctrines.</p>
<p>B.A. Raizberg, L.Sh. Lozovsky and E.B. Starodubtseva</p>	<p>They expressed views on state regulation, economic objectives, influence, and public goods. This process occurs in both centralized and market economies, but the forms of regulation differ significantly. For instance, when considering a centralized economy, it focuses on directive planning and control, whereas a market economy is characterized by budgeting, taxation, crediting, state purchases, and the improvement of legislation.</p>	<p>In the context of market relations, state regulation of the economy is aligned with the objective economic laws of societal development, primarily referring to the law of demand and supply, the law of value, and others. State regulation is directed at ensuring a legal basis for the functioning of the market system, establishing legal and cooperative relations among producers, suppliers, and consumers.</p>

The real sector encompasses the production of material goods, the creation of tangible wealth, and the provision of services. Financial, credit, and stock market activities do not fall within this sector. A significant portion of GDP is generated in the real sector, where industry and services constitute its most important structural divisions. In the material production sector, economic resources are transformed into goods and consumer products. The growth of this sector directly contributes to increasing household incomes, improving living standards, and providing the financial and material foundation for the advancement of education, healthcare, and cultural development.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the aforementioned points, the following conclusions can be drawn: The effective functioning of the economic system depends on the balanced development of the real and financial sectors, as well as the synergistic integration of economic relations among them. A balanced structural policy within the real sector of the economy is essential for sustainable economic growth. In the context of ongoing economic reforms, it is crucial to avoid over-reliance on either market-driven or administrative principles that influence the real sector and the broader economic system. The real sector of the economy must be considered in terms of both positive and negative outcomes, including income inequality, unemployment, and other socio-economic issues. This necessitates a comprehensive socio-economic policy; however, state authorities should not confine their role to implementing only social policies.

The analyzed data suggest that understanding the economic mechanisms of state regulation in the real sector requires studying both the achievements and shortcomings of theoretical approaches. Additionally, gaining insight into the global economic context and drawing lessons from the experiences of developed countries can contribute to the success of ongoing economic reforms. Scientific recommendations derived from further research can serve as a foundation for developing targeted strategies to be implemented in our country.

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14. Author's personal developments.

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

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2025. № 3

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